

Magnetic, Spectral and Thermal Studies on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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Several mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) having the compositions $[M(aa)(tca)]$ and $[M(aa)(tca)L_2]$, where aaH is acetylacetone, tcaH is trichloroacetic acid; L is γ -picoline, imidazole, 2-picoline-N-oxide or thiourea and M is Cu(II) or Ni(II), have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared, electronic spectral data and thermogravimetric measurements. The infrared spectra reveal the presence of uninegative bidentate acetyl acetate and trichloroacetate groups in all these complexes. As the temperature increases, the mixed ligand complexes start decomposing with the loss of neutral donor ligand, followed by trichloroacetate ion and acetylacetone ion in definite steps and ultimately forming MO at 600-675°. Square planar, tetrahedral, distorted octahedral and octahedral structures have been proposed for the complexes, $[Cu(aa)(tca)]$, $[Ni(aa)(tca)]$, $[Cu(aa)(tca)L_2]$ and $[Ni(aa)(tca)L_2]$, respectively.

ISOLATION and characterisation of several mixed ligand complexes of copper(II)¹⁻⁴ and nickel(II)⁵⁻⁹ β -diketonate with neutral hetero donor ligands have been reported in the literature. But reactions of mixed chelate complexes of these metals containing β -diketone and hetero-chelate with neutral donor ligands do not appear to have been studied extensively. The present paper relates to a systematic study of some mixed ligand complexes having the compositions $[M(aa)(tca)]$ and $[M(aa)(tca)L_2]$, where M is Cu(II) or Ni(II), aaH is acetylacetone, tcaH is trichloroacetic acid and L is γ -picoline (γ -pic), imidazole (iz), 2-picoline-N-oxide (2-pic-N-O) or thiourea (tu)⁻¹.

Experimental

$[M(aa)(tca)]$: The mixed chelate complex of copper(II) was obtained by refluxing a mixture of bis(acetylacetonato) copper(II)¹ and trichloroacetic acid in equimolar proportion in chloroform for 10 min. The corresponding nickel(II) complex was isolated after refluxing bis(acetylacetonato) nickel(II)⁷ and trichloroacetic acid in equimolar proportion in ethanol medium for 1 h and keeping the resulting solution overnight. The complexes were filtered, washed with chloroform and ethanol, followed by ether and finally dried in vacuum.

$[M(aa)(tca)L_2]$: The mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) were refluxed separately with γ -picoline, imidazole, 2-picoline-N-oxide or thiourea in 1:2 molar ratio in chloroform and ethanol, respectively for about 1 h. On cooling the

resulting solutions the complexes separated out and were collected as reported above. Under the experimental condition $[Cu(aa)(tca)]$ did not form the desired product with thiourea.

Copper, nickel, chlorine and sulphur were estimated by standard methods. Two complexes only were analysed for nitrogen. (Found: N, 5.28. $[Cu(aa)(tca)(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]$ requires N, 5.47% and Found: N, 11.98. $[Ni(aa)(tca)(iz)_2]$ requires N, 12.27%).

Electrical conductances of $10^{-3}M$ methanolic solutions of these complexes were measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge with dipping electrode cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy magnetic balance at room temperature using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant. Infrared spectra of the complexes as KBr pellets were scanned on a Perkin Elmer 137 Infracord spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol were recorded using Elico CL 24 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric measurements were carried out on a Simultane Thermo Analyse balance, model 429 (W. Germany) at a heating rate of 10°min^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Composition: On the basis of elemental analyses and low molar conductance values (4.2-9.2 mhos) (Table 1) the molecular formulae assigned to the complexes are $[M(aa)(tca)]$ and $[M(aa)(tca)L_2]$.

Magnetic moments: All the copper(II) complexes have magnetic moments ranging between 1.83

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TABLE 1—COLOUR, M.P. AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) AND NICKEL(II)

Compound	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M mhos
			Metal	Halogen		
[Cu(aa)(tca)]	Parrot green	> 250	20.11 (19.54)	33.21 (32.71)	1.83	7.2
[Cu(aa)(tca)(γ -pic) ₂]	Blue	189	12.64 (12.43)	21.33 (20.81)	1.85	8.1
[Cu(aa)(tca)(iz) ₂]	Deep blue	135	12.81 (13.77)	23.49 (23.05)	1.86	8.7
[Cu(aa)(tca)(2-pic-NO) ₂]	Deep green	148	11.28 (11.70)	18.71 (19.58)	1.85	9.2
[Ni(aa)(tca)]	Greenish blue	165	18.73 (18.33)	32.34 (33.21)	3.50	4.2
[Ni(aa)(tca)(γ -pic) ₂]	Blue	210	11.66 (11.59)	21.33 (21.01)	3.25	9.1
[Ni(aa)(tca)(iz) ₂]	Blue	258	12.99 (12.86)	22.79 (23.30)	3.30	7.4
[Ni(aa)(tca)(2-pic-NO) ₂]	Light blue	237	11.28 (10.90)	20.24 (19.75)	3.15	6.2
[Ni(aa)(tca)(tu) ₂]**	Bottle green	205*	12.18 (12.42)	22.40 (22.51)	3.20	8.3

* decomposes without melting.

** % Sulphur, 13.04/(13.54).

and 1.86 B.M. The μ_{eff} value of 3.5 B.M. for the complex [Ni(aa)(tca)] suggests¹⁰ a tetrahedral stereochemistry. The magnetic moments of other nickel(II) complexes lie in the range 3.15-3.30 B.M., which are characteristics of octahedral nickel(II) complexes¹⁰.

Infrared spectra: Bonding sites of the ligands and probable structure of the complexes are elucidated by comparing the infrared spectra of the metal complexes with those of the ligands. In the spectra of the mixed chelate complexes, [M(aa)(tca)], the occurrence of bands due to $\nu(C=O)$ around 1640-1570 cm^{-1} and $\nu(C=C)$ around 1525-1515 cm^{-1} clearly indicates uninegative bidentate nature of acetylacetonate ion⁵. The bands assignable to $\nu_{asym}(OCO)$ and $\nu_{sym}(OCO)$ of trichloroacetate ion at 1625 and 1445 cm^{-1} , respectively are observed around 1690-1620 and 1570-1470 cm^{-1} , respectively in the mixed chelate complexes. The changes in these modes on complexation suggest¹¹⁻¹⁵ that

introduction of neutral donor ligands, L, significant changes in $\nu(C=O)$ and $\nu(C=C)$ of acetylacetonate ion, $\nu_{asym}(OCO)$ and $\nu_{sym}(OCO)$ of trichloroacetate ion (Table 2) and the ligand bands are noticed in the infrared spectra of the adducts confirming bonding of the neutral donors to the metal ions.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of [Cu(aa)(tca)] exhibit a broad absorption band at 14080 cm^{-1} suggesting a square planar stereochemistry¹⁶⁻¹⁹. This is supported by the fact that tetrahedral copper(II) complexes do not show²⁰ d-d absorption bands in the region 10000-20000 cm^{-1} . The room temperature magnetic moment value of 1.83 B.M. for the complex also favours the square planar structure²¹. The complexes [Cu(aa)(tca)L₂] display one broad absorption band in the region 13000-15800 cm^{-1} characteristic of distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes^{22,23}. The complex [Ni(aa)(tca)] gives electronic spectral bands at 11400 and 16130 cm^{-1} regions indicating a tetrahedral configuration²⁴. Other nickel(II) complexes show bands around 11100, 16600 and 25600 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P) (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively characteristic of octahedral nickel(II) complexes²⁵⁻²⁶.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF COMPLEXES OF Cu(II) and Ni(II)

Compound	aa		tca	
	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(C-C)$	$\nu_{asym}OCO$	$\nu_{sym}OCO$
[Cu(aa)(tca)]	1640	1525	1690	1570
[Cu(aa)(tca)(γ -pic) ₂]	1560	1438	1620	1508
[Cu(aa)(tca)(iz) ₂]	1610	1495	1670	1545
[Cu(aa)(tca)(2-pic-NO) ₂]	1610	1490	1655	1565
[Ni(aa)(tca)]	1570	1515	1620	1470
[Ni(aa)(tca)(γ -pic) ₂]	1560	1510	1595	1465
[Ni(aa)(tca)(iz) ₂]	1565	1510	1595	1465
[Ni(aa)(tca)(2-pic-NO) ₂]	1560	1510	1610	1460
[Ni(aa)(tca)(tu) ₂]	1568	1512	1608	1465

trichloroacetate group behaves as an uninegative bidentate ligand in these complexes. With the

Thermogravimetric measurements: The thermogravimetric measurements of some mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) (Table 3) studied by TG and DTA techniques provide further evidence regarding coordination of the ligands. The complexes start losing weight at 110-170° with the loss of neutral donor ligand, trichloroacetate ion and acetylacetonate ion in the given order, ultimately forming copper oxide or nickel oxide at 600-675° with an exothermic peak in the DTA derivatograph. The loss in weight of the complexes at different temperatures accompanied by exothermic

TABLE 3—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC MEASUREMENTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) AND NICKEL(II)

Compound	Initial decomposition temp. °C	TGA		Species formed	DTA peaks
		Temp. °C	% Loss Found/(Calcd.)		
[Cu(aa)(tca)(γ -pic) ₂]	160	160-220	20.92 (18.19)	Cu(aa)(tca)L	Endo.
		220-330	51.30 (52.29)	Cu(aa)(tca) _{0.5}	Endo.
		330-395	60.84 (60.17)	Cu(aa)(tca) _{0.25}	Endo.
		395-490	65.86 (67.41)	Cu(aa)	Endo.
		490-660	83.12 (84.44)	CuO	Exo.
[Cu(aa)(tca)(iz) ₂]	110	110-115	13.44 (14.76)	Cu(aa)(tca)L	Exo.
		115-120	28.42 (29.49)	Cu(aa)(tca)	Exo.
		120-180	48.81 (47.07)	Cu(aa)(tca) _{0.5}	Exo.
		180-225	57.59 (55.83)	Cu(aa)(tca) _{0.25}	Endo.
		225-400	74.16 (75.48)	Cu(aa) _{0.5}	Exo.
		400-540	79.98 (80.91)	Cu(aa) _{0.25}	Endo.
		540-660	88.36 (86.33)	CuO	Exo.
[Ni(aa)(tca)(2-pic-NO) ₂]	170	170-200	10.83 (10.12)	Ni(aa)(tca)L _{1.5}	Endo.
		220-240	30.37 (31.54)	Ni(aa)(tca)L _{0.5}	Exo.
		240-475	74.74 (75.27)	Ni(aa) _{0.75}	Exo.
		475-530	79.80 (79.92)	Ni(aa) _{0.5}	Exo.
		530-600	82.40 (86.11)	NiO	Exo.
[Ni(aa)(tca)(tu) ₂]	160	160-180	16.30 (16.11)	Ni(aa)(tca)L	Endo.
		180-250	48.90 (49.36)	Ni(aa)(tca) _{0.5}	Exo.
		250-435	56.72 (57.94)	Ni(aa)(tca) _{0.25}	Exo.
		435-490	65.19 (66.51)	Ni(aa)	Exo.
		490-675	85.32 (84.19)	NiO	Exo.

or endothermic peak closely agrees with the calculated loss in weight indicating the authenticity of the formulations of the mixed ligand complexes.

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